

Analysis of portfolio Risk and Return with reference to IT securities in India

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ABSTRACT

The study's major goal is to teach investors a basic understanding of mutual fund investing and to inspire them to finance in zones where they may get the best return on their money. This research aids us in comprehending how businesses diversify their operations across industries and enterprises in order to optimise revenues while minimising risks. A collection of investments run by a business or an individual will be termed as portfolio. A financial organisation will normally undertake its own investment analysis while establishing an investment portfolio, whereas a private individual may engage the services of a financial advisor or a financial institution that provides portfolio management services. This paper aims to provide a brief theoretical explanation with examples for evaluating the returns and associated risk of individual shares, as well as the portfolio of individual shares. The stock exchange not only allows for free share transfers, but it also conducts ongoing evaluations of the securities traded on the market. The goal of this paper is to inspect the "Risk and Return Analysis" of Selected Indian IT Stocks. An investor can use the return on an investment portfolio to assess the investment's financial performance.

Keywords: India, Portfolio, Risk, Return, Shares, Standard Deviation.

1. INTRODUCTION:

The risk-reward association is a essential concept in all parts of life, not just financial analysis. If a decision is to lead to benefit maximization, individuals/institutions must assess the combined effect on predictable (future) return or benefit, so also the risk/cost. The necessity for predicted return/benefit to be proportional to risk/cost is referred to as the "risk-return trade-off" in finance. A company with high market price isn't always the best stock to buy. It could be expensive or have no future growth potential. Likewise, a company that does well one year might not be the best to invest in the next. On the other hand, a firm that has been performing poorly for a long time may be the best buy since its shares are undervalued and it has high growth potential, therefore a risk or return analysis can help an investor make a profitable savings. The risk and return trade-off states that as risk rises, so does the possible return. An investor must find a balance between his or her aim for the lowest risk and the biggest attainable return. Before investing unavoidable capital in a stock, any reasonable investor evaluates the risk associated with that asset. The actual return on a stock may differ from the predicted return.

Aspects of risk and return are present in the financial decision. The link between risk and return is known as the “risk-return trade-off”, which means that bigger gains can only be obtained by taking on more risk. For better returns, an investor must understand that, the same can be done by embracing a higher level of risk. Risk and return are inversely proportional; as one rises, the other rises as well. The consequences for the financial management in evaluating a potential investment project are that an effective choice about the project's worth to the firm cannot be made solely on the basis of its rate of return; the project's level of risk must also be taken into account. The risk-reward trade-off lies at the heart of investment (Mcmenamin, 1999).

The return on an investment and the danger of an investment are fundamental notions in finance because so much of it revolves around the risk-reward tradeoff. The financial outcome for the investor is the return on an investment. Each possible shilling return can be assigned a probability by investors. They can create a probability distribution for the investment's future returns. A probability distribution is a collection of all potential shilling returns from an investment, together with their likelihood.

The concept of risk and return analysis is crucial to the investing and financial processes. Every financial decision entails some level of risk. One might expect a 15 percent annual return on his investment, but the risk of "not being able to reach 15 percent return" will always exist. Because all investing entails some risk, return is simply a reward for doing so. Risk and return are two important factors that influence stock values. The bigger the assumed risk, the higher the reward. Low-risk investments, such as government securities, will yield a low rate of return. Any reasonable investor would assess the risk associated with a specific stock, and having a good understanding of risk allows him to design his portfolio to reduce the risk of the investment. Income, capital appreciation, or a positive inflation hedge can all contribute to a favourable return on investment. The degree of risk is determined by the characteristics of an asset, investment instruments, investment method, and other factors. The greater the risk, the larger the variety of probable outcomes.

2. SCOPE OF THE STUDY

- The study consists of 5 companies from selected sector information technology.
- The stock price and index movement for the period of 2015 to 2020 have been considered for the calculation of Beta.
- The research is limited to a comparison of the stock market performance with the performance of five top corporations in the information technology (IT) sector. The firm listed on BSE is considered for the study.
- The beta is calculated based on the return for the limited period as share price for years
- An only a secondary source of data is used for the study, which limits with the scope of the research work

3. OBJECTIVES:

- To assess the risk and potential return of a chosen stock from the IT sector..
- Using tools and methodologies, assess the risk of selected securities
- To study the systematic risk involved in selected company securities.
- To guide an investor in the selection of security

4. METHODOLOGY:

Secondary data is used in this investigation, acquired from the BSE website, as well as data collected from other sources such as the internet, such as journals and company websites, and internet articles.

The acquired data is sorted out for the analysis. The following are the tools and approaches that were employed in the analysis:

- 1) Risk= $\sqrt{\sum D^2/(n-1)}$.
- 2) Return =close price - previous price / previous price *100.
- 3) Co-efficient of variation = Risk / Return.

5. LITERATURE REVIEW :

The researcher Poornima, S. (2017) [1], employed the “capital asset pricing model” to investigate the relationship between risk and return. In his research, he focuses on two industries: automobiles and information technology. Which companies are listed on the NSE? According to his research, vehicle firms have performed better and seen increased market expansion.

The study by Itoe et al. (2016) [2] on the performance of the Doula Stock Exchange is particularly impressive. From 2006 through 2015, a ten-year study was undertaken. They came to the conclusion that the stock market serves as a guide for investors looking to invest and aids in financial decision-making. Furthermore, they stated that the Doula stock exchange market supports significantly to Cameroon's economic growth, with this favourable trend beginning in 2010 when the stock exchange launched the government treasury bong.

In her paper on “Quality in Governance of Demutualized Stock Exchanges versus Mutualized Stock Exchanges—A Case Study”, the researcher Roopa (2016) [3][4] focused on an important topic. The National Stock Exchange (NSE) and the Bombay Stock Exchange (BSE), two of India's most important stock markets, were examined in this study. The emphasis was on market quality and stock exchange governance. According to the findings, the NSE has a higher-quality market than the BSE. According to the report, NSE played a critical role in modernizing Indian stock markets through implementing innovative technologies and therefore lowering costs for investors.

Krishnaprabha *et al.* (2015) [5] in their work “A study on risk and return analysis of selected stocks in India” exemplified the risk and return analysis of the IT, Automobile, Pharmaceutical, and Fast Moving Consumer Goods industries. The study comprised at least five companies from each sector and lasted five years (from January 1, 2010 to December 31, 2014), with Beta, Standard Deviation, and Variety.

Rashinkar, S., and Divya, U. (2014) [6] carried out a study on “Market Risk Analysis of Selected Banking Stocks in India”. Their study limited to 5 Indian nationalized banks. They are - The State Bank of India (SBI), the Industrial Development Bank of India (IDBI), the

Syndicate Bank (SB), the Punjab National Bank (PNB), and the Bank of Baroda (BB). The study lasted one year (from July 1, 2013 to March 31, 2014), with Beta Coefficient as the analysis instrument. According to the study, the betas of SBI, IDBI, and SB were all moving away from market. The scenario is indicating that these stocks move against the market and are less prone to market risk. PNB and BB, on the contrary, have numerous betas. This suggests that these stocks were exposed to a significant amount of market risk.

Emenike, K. O., and Ani, W. U. (2014) [7] conducted a study on the volatility of Nigeria's banking industry stock returns. Access Bank Plc, ETI Plc, Diamond Bank Plc, Fidelity Bank Plc, and GTB Plc are among the best capitalized and liquid banks on the Nigerian stock exchange. Skye Bank Plc, Sterling Bank Plc, United Bank for Africa, Union Bank Plc, and Zenith Bank Plc are among the other banks. From January 3, 2006, to December 31, 2012, the study was conducted. It shows that returns in the Nigerian banking industry are very erratic and that volatility persists throughout the sample period.

Chawla (2001) [9] was conducted an investigative research on the stability of beta in the Indian stock market. The study analysed monthly data from 36 stocks from March 1996 to March 2000, a period of four years. To explore the same, the researchers employed dummy variables for the slope coefficient and incorporated a time variable in the regression. The study concluded that beta was unstable over time.

Gupta (1981) [10] Return on New Equity Issues was a study that looked at the difference between new equity issue returns and existing equity share returns. He advised investors that the return on a new issuance of equity shares, which comprises surpluses and capital appreciation, should be studied individually, especially for young companies, due to the fact that the rate of return on new issues fluctuates over time.

6. INDUSTRY OVERVIEW:

The field of information technology (IT) is a knowledge-based one. IT can be defined as the use of hardware, services, and infrastructure to establish stores, share data, and exploit data in various forms to achieve a variety of business goals. The IT sector offers tremendous potential for accelerating the country's economic growth. Our governance has become more efficient as a result of information technology. It improves information availability, offers access to services, protects consumers, improves skill development and training, advances health-care delivery, and promotes transparency. The Indian government has acknowledged the importance of the IT industry in the country's economic progress. Technological revolutions might present governments with unforeseen opportunities. In the information technology revolution, India, as a developing country in terms of economic growth, appears to have discovered such an opportunity as an increasingly preferred place for bespoke software development. India's software success has sparked discussion about whether other developing countries can follow in its footsteps, as well as whether this poses a competitive threat to developed-world software industries.

Over the last few years, labour arbitrage has been the Indian software industry's competitive advantage. However, MNCs that are copying the Indian outsourcing model and building up captive bases in the country appear to be posing a challenge to this. A new trend of 'reshoring' has emerged, in which US firms are increasingly returning operations that were previously outsourced to the US.

The software industry started in 1953 and the first software provider is computer Usage Company in 1955, IBM and UNIVAC are the commercial computer dears in the 1960s. In 1959 computer Sciences Corporation was founded which helped to develop advanced computer technology and automatic processing technology. Now the worldwide size of the software industry is estimated at USD\$407.3 billion.

7. DATA ANALYSIS AND INTERPRETATION

7.1 ANALYSIS OF RETURN

Table 7.1.1 Calculation of Average Return of HCL Technologies

Year	Open Price(P0)	Close Price(P1)	(P1-P0)	(P1-P0)/P0*100
2015	1596	860.05	-735.95	-46.1122
2016	848	827.4	-20.6	-2.42925
2017	825	890.65	65.65	7.957576
2018	885.25	962.55	77.3	8.731997
2019	965	568.25	-396.75	-41.114
2020	572	404.95	-167.05	-29.2045
Total return				-102.17

Average return = $-102.17/5$
 = -17.028

Figure 7.1.1.1: a chart showing returns of the HCL Technologies.

Interpretation: The table above presenting the calculated return of HCL Technologies for one year. The average return is -17.0284. Wherein maximum returns are in the year 2018

Table 7.1.2 Average Return of Infosys

Year	Open Price(P0)	Close Price(P1)	(P1-P0)	P1-P0/P0*100
2015	1967.8	1095.85	-871.95	-44.3109
2016	1100	1010.7	-89.3	-8.1182
2017	1012	1039.3	27.3	2.6976
2018	1040	659.85	-380.15	-36.5529
2019	661	731.75	70.75	10.7035
2020	733.6	585.45	-148.15	-20.1949
Total return				-95.7758

Average return= $-95.7758/6$

= -15.96263218

Figure 7.1.2.1 chart showing returns of the Infosys

Interpretation:The “HCL Technologies Company” - Returns. The average return is -15.9626. Wherein maximum returns are in the year 2019

Table 7.1.3 Average Return of TCS

Year	Open Price(P0)	Close Price(P1)	(P1-P0)	P1-P0/P0*100
2015	2554.35	2433.35	-121	-4.7370
2016	2432.1	2361.95	-70.15	-2.8843
2017	2365	2700.4	335.4	14.1818
2018	2689.8	1893.55	-796.25	-29.6026
2019	1905	2161.3	256.3	13.4541
2020	2170	1654.4	-515.6	-23.7604
Total return				-33.3484

Average return = $-33.3484/6$

$$= -5.56$$

Figure 7.1.3.1 chart showing returns of the TCS

Interpretation: The return of TCSCompany is shown in the table given above. The average return is -5.56. Wherein maximum returns are in the year 2017.

Table 7.1.4 Avg. Return of Tech Mahindra

Year	Open Price(P0)	Close Price(P1)	(P1-P0)	P1-P0/P0*100
2015	2591.75	518.2	-2073.55	-80.0058
2016	522.95	488.7	-34.25	-6.5494
2017	494	503.85	9.85	1.9939
2018	500	721.1	221.1	44.22
2019	715	762.6	47.6	6.6573
2020	764.5	520.65	-243.85	-31.8967
Total return				-65.5806

Average return = $-65.5806 / 6$

$$= -10.930$$

Figure 7.1.4.1 chart showing returns of the Tech Mahindra

Interpretation: The average returns of Tech Mahindra are -10.930. The maximum returns is in the third year i.e. 2019

Table 7.1.5 Average Return - Wipro

Year	Open Price(P0)	Close Price(P1)	(P1-P0)	P1-P0/P0*100
2015	553	555.95	2.95	0.5334
2016	558	474	-84	-15.0537
2017	475	313.4	-161.6	-34.0210
2018	313.4	330.25	16.85	5.3765
2019	334.5	245.95	-88.55	-26.4723
2020	247	180	-67	-27.1255
Total return				-96.7626

Average return = $-96.7626941/6$
 $= -16.1271$

Figure 7.1.5.1 chart showing returns of the Wipro

Interpretation: The average returns of Wipro is -16.13. The maximum returns is in the third year i.e. 2018.

7.2 SENSEX

7.2.1 Table showing the calculation of variance and standard deviation of SENSEX

Year	Return(R)	Average Return (R-)	d= (R – $\bar{R}$)	d ²
2015	-4.9780	3.4843	-8.462268486	71.60998793
2016	2.0112	3.4843	-1.473085392	2.169980572
2017	27.5004	3.4843	24.01611505	576.773782
2018	5.8965	3.4843	2.412167736	5.818553187
2019	14.0810	3.4843	10.59668074	112.2896427
2020	-23.6053	3.4843	-27.08960965	733.846951
				$\sum d^2 = 1502.508897$

Variance = $1/n-1(\sum d^2)$

$$1/6-1(1502.508897)$$

$$=300.5017795$$

Standard deviation= $\sqrt{\text{variance}}$

$$\sqrt{300.5017795}$$

$$= 17.3349$$

7.3 Table showing standard deviation and an average return of selected companies

Sl.No	COMPANY	STANDARD DEVIATION	AVERAGE RETURN
1	HCL Technologies	24.8	-17.0284
2	Infosys Ltd.	21.75	-15.9626
3	TATA consultancy services	18.266	-5.55807
4	Tech Mahindra	41.828	-10.9301
5	Wipro	16.5	-16.1271

Figure 7.3.1 chart showing the Standard Deviation of the selected companies

7.4 Table Depicting All Calculated Values

	HCL Technology	Infosys	TATA Consultancy Services	Tech Mahindra	Wipro
Average Returns	-17.0284	-15.9626	-5.55807	-10.9301	-16.1271
Standard Deviations	24.8	21.75	18.266	41.828	16.5
Covariance	160.2387	170.6731	183.2914	295.9741	-55.3538
Beta	0.639885	0.681552	0.731941	1.18192	-0.22105

Figure 5.5.1: Beta Values of the Stocks

It should be observed that, with the exception of Wipro, all of the scripts in the above table have a positive Beta value. This indicates that the stock's return moves in lockstep with the market's. Polaris' stock price rises and falls in the opposite direction of the market. Investors with a lower risk tolerance can choose securities with a low beta, which signals a lower market response and is therefore less dangerous.

8. FINDINGS

- The average return for the company "HCL Technologies" is -17.0284, the risk is 24.8, and the coefficient of variance is 0.447268. The highest market price was \$1596 in 2015, while the lowest market price was \$576 in 2020.
- The company "Infosys ltd" has a -15.9626 average return, a risk of 21.75, and a coefficient of variation of 0.5430. In 2015, the highest market price was \$167.8; in 2019, the lowest market price was \$661.
- The firm "TATA Consultancy Services" has a -5.558 average return, an 18.266 risk, and a 06945 coefficient of variation. The highest market price was 2689.8 in 2018, and the lowest market price was 1905 in the same year.
- The average return for the company "Wipro" is -16.1271, the risk is 16.5, and the coefficient of variance is 0.2386. In 2015, the highest market price was \$553; in 2018, the lowest market price was 313.4.
- HCL Technologies, Infosys, TCS, and Tech Mahindra all have a positive beta rating, which means their stock prices move in lockstep with the market index. Wipro, on the other hand, has negative beta values.
- The average return for the company "Infosys ltd" is -15.9626; the risk is 21.75, and the coefficient of variance is 0.5430. In 2015, the highest market price was \$167.8; in 2019, the lowest market price was \$661.
- The average return for the company "TATA Consultancy Services" is -5.558, the risk is 18.266, and the coefficient of variation is 06945. In 2018, the highest market price was 2689.8; in 2019, the lowest market price was 1905.

- The average return for the company "Wipro" is -16.1271, the risk is 16.5, and the coefficient of variance is 0.2386. In 2015, the highest market price was \$553; in 2018, the lowest market price was 313.4.
- HCL Technologies, Infosys, TCS, and Tech Mahindra all have a positive beta rating, which means their stock prices move in lockstep with the market index. Wipro, on the other hand, has negative beta values.

9. SUGGESTION

- If an investor wants to invest in equities that have lower risks and higher returns, he should look for assets with a Beta of less than +1.00. Stocks with a Beta of less than +1.00 are thought to be more conservative investments.
 - The securities with the highest returns and the lowest risk should be considered by the investor. Investing in TCS equities is hence recommended. Investors should hold securities that give high returns with less risk.
1. As an investor, notice that the securities have a negative correlation.
 2. Fundamental study of securities should be prioritized by investors.
 3. Industrial policy plays an important role in enabling economic progress.
 4. Having two or more securities in your portfolio reduces the danger of unsystematic risk.

10. CONCLUSION

The risk-return analysis assists the investor in deciding which assets to invest in based on his personal preferences. This type of analysis gives details regarding the risk and return performance of numerous market stocks. The relationship between market fluctuations and Scrip prices is the subject of this article. Fundamental and technical analysis has been used despite the difficulty of observing a pattern for price changes. According to fundamental analysis, the companies' financial situation and performance are in accordance with current market prices. However, no single method can be said to be sufficient for analysing and interpreting swings, although they can assist the investor in defining trends to some extent. Based on the calculations, investors can infer that they should continue to analyse the market, which will assist them in selecting the best companies in which to put their money.

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